

Psychological Analysis of Females' Attitude toward Entrepreneurship as a Career ...

Psychological Analysis of Females' Attitude toward Entrepreneurship as a Career in Azad Kashmir

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Abstract

This study intends to make. "Psychological Analysis of Females Attitude towards Entrepreneurship as a Career in Azad Kashmir" The objectives of this research was to investigate relation between family type and women entrepreneurship, to determine entrepreneurs' barrier faced by female graduates and rank them. Population of current study consisted of females' graduate students of three universities of Azad Jammu & Kashmir. The self developed validated questionnaire was used to collect data. The reliability value as ($\alpha = .726$). Data was analyzed by applying regression, chi square. This study found that there is a significant positive relationship between the selected factors with entrepreneurial career aspirations. Attitude toward entrepreneurship was reported to have the strongest association with entrepreneurial career aspirations. In short, the findings of this study provided greater understanding in predicting students' entrepreneurial behavior. There is a need for a well-established entrepreneurial ecosystem which will encourage and empower females to create their own businesses.

Keywords: entrepreneurial career aspirations, attitude toward entrepreneurship

Introduction

In Azad Kashmir Women's entrepreneurship is a topic that receives little attention. The governments appear unable to address the growing difficulties of female entrepreneurship. They are dealing with a variety of issues, including economic, cultural, sociological, and theological issues. Psychological disorders exacerbate the situation, making people untrustworthy in commercial transactions. Silence, despair, neglect, social isolation, and non-

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participative conduct are some of the causes of female psychological illnesses that have an impact on their ability to run a business. The purpose of this research is to uncover female psychological analysis for entrepreneurship. Females from middle-class homes in Azad Jammu and Kashmir are very worried about their families and try to contribute to boosting the household income. To attain this goal, they participate in a variety of entrepreneurial activities, some of which are high-risk. These elements place individuals under a lot of stress and pressure, which leads to a lot of psychological problems. It elucidates some of the psychosocial challenges that female entrepreneurs face.

"Career aspirations" are defined as an individual's expressed career-related goals or choices (Rsojewski, 2005). Under ideal circumstances, career aspirations refer to an individual's direction toward a chosen career goal. Simply put, "professional goals" convey information about a person's hopes and interests, free of constraints imposed by reality. (Hellenga, Aber, & Rhodes, 2002). Women often distinguish barriers and role conflicts as obstacle in their career development process (Brown & Barbosa, 2001). Women's common impediments include sex-typing of employment and sex bias, both of which they felt powerless to control. Poor academic attainment, insufficient professional skills, and a lack of mobility are all major reasons for women's failure in the workforce. Despite these assumptions among women, evidence from recent studies revealed that females showed a greater interest in a broader number of jobs and exhibited more gender-role flexibility in their professional aspirations than males (Francis, 2002).

Women's "professional aspirations" have gradually developed throughout the twentieth century, resulting in greater workforce participation rates. Over time, a variety of circumstances have influenced and limited women's "professional aspirations" and career advancement. Women's career choices and the factors that influence them are important to investigate, especially since most studies show that women continue to work in lower-paying, traditionally female-oriented jobs. In order to stay successful and efficient, career development must be addressed in a way that is consistent with the needs of a more diverse workforce, and organisations must pay attention to women's career difficulties. (Patawardhan et al, 2016).

Females are responsible for the administration of the complete collection of difficulties related to family in current society. It has also been noticed that females pursue occupations part-time till they marry, and another reason for females' persuasion of careers in our society is the lack of economic necessities, as doing so under normal circumstances would make females culturally disliked. Females tend to settle down with their duty as family managers after marriage, recognising that their career orientation does not match their career ambitions (Ilyas, 2014).

The absence of a mother during a child's early years has a negative impact on the child's emotional and psychological development. Obviously, more time spent at the workplace meant less time spent with the kids. Females were also found to be incompetent and unable to cope in a high-stress job environment since they must fulfil their role as mothers, according to the research. Female reproductive abilities may also deteriorate as a result of severe strain placed on them, making them hesitant to seek employment in high-demand situations (Shoaib Khan & Khan ,2010).

Some of the unique attitudes, such as a desire to learn for the sake of learning, a lack of fear

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of business risks or failures, and high self-esteem, are psychological characteristics. Women entrepreneurs have the native knowledge and abilities needed to run a business. However, they confront substantial challenges like as social hurdles, a lack of proper education, and a lack of understanding of legal requirements, all of which function as roadblocks to successful entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurs are now looking for positive social reinforcement to help them enhance their abilities. However, for a business in its mature stage, the ability of the entrepreneurs to continuously innovate and their risk-taking abilities are critical considerations. "Proper training and education for women entrepreneurs through Entrepreneurship Development programs will help them to adapt to modern business practices, facilitating changes in products, processes, marketing, and organization structure and marketing. (Digan et al. 2019).

Statement of the problem

The concept of entrepreneurship is a new concept associated with women entrepreneurship in the world, certainly there are some countries that are lagging behind in women entrepreneurship, Azad Jammu and Kashmir is one of them, the researcher has observed that women in these areas had a lot of potential and scope to become an entrepreneur but mostly they opted teaching as a profession so she decided to give an understanding of the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs. The objective of this research is to investigate aspirations of women of this region. Understanding the ways how these women within a traditional Muslim society are able to overcome cultural, gender and government constrains and may help to motivate women in other and similar societies to establish their own businesses.

Objectives

1. To find relation between family type and women entrepreneurship
2. To determine entrepreneurship barriers faced by female graduates,
3. To find out the challenges faced by female in entrepreneurship?
4. To identify the female career aspiration and rank them.

Methodology

The current study's participants were female graduate students from three Azad Jammu and Kashmir universities. The participants in this study were female graduate students from Azad Jammu and Kashmir. 1. University of Azad Jammu & Kashmir Muzaffarabad. 2. Poonch university rawalakot. 3. Women University of Azad Jammu & Kashmir Bagh. The sample was chosen using non-probability sampling techniques. The students were given 450 questionnaires by the researcher. After reviewing relevant literature and consulting with an expert, the researcher created a detailed questionnaire based on the study's objectives. Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided than Disagree, and Strongly Disagree were the responses on a five-point scale. The researcher used questionnaire as the main instrument to collect data from the respondents. After applying Cronbach's alpha it was concluded that all the statement of instrument existed on a suitable reliability as alpha =.726. The validity of the research instruments was ensured through taking experts' opinion. And then questionnaire was finalized.

Data Analysis The data was analyzed by various test using spss software, the results are mentioned below

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Table No 1 I have an aspiration to be successful entrepreneurs

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.011 ^a	6	.001
Likelihood Ratio	22.439	6	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	12.181	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	418		

a. 5 cells (41.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .40.

The chisquare table shows that female have an aspiration to be a successful entrepreneurs hence Chi square value is 24.011(3)=.001. This proves that majority female have aspiration to be successful entrepreneurs.

Table No 02 I am sure that i will run my own business in future

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.807 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	23.475	6	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	.017	1	.896
N of Valid Cases	418		

a. 5 cells (41.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .58.

The chisquare table shows that majority of female sure that they will run their own business in future hence Chi square value is 25.807(3) =.000. This proves that majority believes that they will run their own business in future.

Table No 3 Generally, society members accept an entrepreneurial career of women

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	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.535 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.844	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	16.275	1	.000
N of Valid Cases		418	

a. 5 cells (41.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .47.

The chisquare table shows that generally, society members accept an entrepreneurial career of women hence Chi square value is 32.535(3) =.000. This proves that majority believes that generally, society members accept an entrepreneurial career of women.

Table No 4 Social setup is a barrier for female own choice of profession

Social setup is a barrier for female own choice of profession		SA	SDA	UD	Total
Type of family	Joint	132	60	25	217
	nuclear	99	62	25	186
	separated	7	2	3	12
	any other	0	3	0	3
Total		238	127	53	418

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Table No 4 displays crosstabs statistics where type of family is shown on X Axis while frequency is shown on Y axis, large majority of the respondents from Joint family had opinion that social setup is a barrier for female own choice of profession second a large number of the respondents from nuclear family had opinion social setup is a barrier for female own choice of profession as shown in the bar against joint and nuclear type of family.

Table No 5 Type of family & the choice of profession

Type of family	If you given the choice what profession would you like to do?								Total
	0	Teachin g	Medical	Engineer ing	Banking	Own business	Working in ngo,s	Any other	
Joint	0	110	45	13	7	26	6	10	217
Nuclear	1	87	44	8	9	25	6	6	186
Separated	0	6	3	0	1	2	0	0	12
Any other	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	3
Total	1	203	94	21	17	53	12	17	418

Table No 05 displays crosstabs statistics where type of family is shown on X Axis while frequency is shown on Y axis, large majority of the respondents from Joint family had opinion that if they have given the choice to choose a profession then they choose teaching as a profession 110 number of respondent respond that they wanted to become a teacher , after teaching large number of the respondent chose medical as a profession 45 respondent respond that they wanted to choose medical profession and also reasonable number of respondents choose own business as a profession Second a large number of the respondents from nuclear family had opinion that if they have given the choice to choose a profession then they choose teaching as a profession , after teaching large number of the respondent chose medical as a profession. And also reasonable number of respondents choose own business as

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a profession as shown in the bar against joint and nuclear type of family. so the trend in both type of family is almost similar. Amongst 418 respondents 203 respondents respond that if they have given the choice they choose teaching as a profession, 94 respondent choose medical as a profession and 53 respondents choose own business as a profession

Table 06 Relationship of career aspiration and family type and size

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.151 ^a	.023	.018	2.71233

a. Predictors: (Constant), Family members, Type of family

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	71.343	2	35.672	4.849	.008 ^b
	Residual	3053.049	415	7.357		
	Total	3124.392	417			

a. Dependent Variable: career aspiration entrepreneurship

b. Predictors: (Constant), Family members, Type of family

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.893	.315		9.187	.000
	Type of family	.722	.239	.156	3.025	.003
	Family members	.090	.269	.017	.336	.737

a. Dependent Variable: career aspiration entrepreneurship

Table No 07 displayed the relationships between career aspirations and some demographic variables like family type and family size. R-square shows that the model is a poor fit but there is a significant relationship between career aspirations and family type as shown in X^2 35.672, F 4.849 with p-value is less than 5%. Type of family is significant however a Family member is insignificant variable.

Table No 8 Relationship of Career aspirations with Entrepreneurship attitude, family choice, barriers to career aspiration, personal choice.

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Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.639 ^a	.408	.402	2.11619

a. Predictors: (Constant), Entrepreneurship attitude, family choice, barriers to career asp, personal choice

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1274.870	4	318.717	71.170	.000 ^b
	Residual	1849.523	413	4.478		
	Total	3124.392	417			

a. Dependent Variable: career aspiration entrepreneurship

b. Predictors: (Constant), Entrepreneurship attitude, family choice, barriers to career aspiration , personal choice

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.115	.270		-.424	.671
	Personal choice	-.022	.045	-.022	-.485	.628
	Barriers to career asp	.056	.044	.055	1.273	.204
	Family choice	.309	.093	.142	3.319	.001
	Enterprenuership attitude	.375	.026	.590	14.520	.000

a. Dependent Variable: career aspiration entrepreneurship

Table No 8 the model summery demonstrated that the model is appropriately fit and adjusted R² is about 0.40, i.e. in response variable about 40% variation is due to regressions included in model. Similarly analysis of variance also describes that model is a good fit as F-statistic is significant with P-value less than 5%. Multiple regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationship between career aspirations and family choice, personal choice barriers to career aspirations, entrepreneurship attitude as potential predictors. It is observed that career aspirations are positively and significantly correlated with the criterion indicating that personal choice and barriers have least relationship with career aspirations while family choice and entrepreneurship attitude is significantly associated as p-value is less than 5%.

ANALYSIS OF OPEN ENDED QUESTION

Open ended questions were analyzed by content/ response analysis.

The question was since your childhood which profession was more admired at home or

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school majority of the respondents response that in their childhood the medical profession was more admired at home because it give a high social status, after medical second large number of respondents had response that in their childhood teaching is more admired at home for girls, their parents thought that teaching would be a good career for their daughter, it is also less expensive also. And teaching is also a noble profession. Sometime teaching profession is tradition in their families, some barriers are also there which affect their career choices. After this reasonable of respondents choose entrepreneurship,

Which profession your peers admire more (name) Majority of the female respond that their peer admired medical field, after medial field a large number of female respond that teaching profession is more admired by their peer. Some female have respond that business is admired by their parents.

SUMMARY

The aim of this research is to investigate aspirations of women of this region. Understanding the ways how these “women within a traditional Muslim society are able to overcome cultural, gender and government constrains is important and may help to motivate women in other and similar societies to establish their own businesses. The objectives of the study was, to identify the female career aspiration and rank them. To find relation between family type and women entrepreneurship. Determine entrepreneurship barrier faced by female graduates. Total of 450 female students were surveyed from 3 universities of Azad Jammu & Kashmir through questionnaire. Some of the items of the questioner were open ended and some were close ended. The questionnaire was pilot tested producing the reliability value as ($\alpha = .726$). Data was analyzed by applying regression, chi square, with the help of SPSS 23. The study found that Career aspirations are positively and significantly correlated. Personal choice and barriers have least relationship with career aspirations while family choice and entrepreneurship attitude is significantly associated. The relationships between career aspirations and some demographic variables like family type and family size. There is a significant relationship between career aspirations and family type $X^2 35.672$, $df 4.849$ with p-value is less than 5%. Type of family is significant however family members are insignificant variable. This study found that there is a significant positive relationship between the selected factors with entrepreneurial career aspirations. Attitude toward entrepreneurship was reported to have the strongest association with entrepreneurial career aspirations.

FINDINGS

- 1.** The study found that majority of the respondents prefer to choose teaching as a profession, from the total 418 respondents 203 respondents respond that if they have given the choice they prefer to choose teaching as a profession. After teaching profession 94 respondents respond that they prefer to choose medical profession and 53 respondents choose to run their own business.
- 2.** The Study found that career aspirations are positively and significantly correlated. Personal choice and barriers have least relationship with career aspirations while family choice and entrepreneurship attitude is significantly associated as p-value is less than 5%.
- 3.** The study found that the relationships between career aspirations and some demographic

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variables like family type and family size. There is a significant relationship between career aspirations and family type as shown in X^2 35.672, F 4.849 with p-value is less than 5%. Type of family is significant however Family members are insignificant variable.

4. The study found that Female have an aspiration to be successful entrepreneurs. Hence chi square value is **24.011(3) = .001**. This proves that majority of female have aspiration to be successful entrepreneurs.

5. The study found that majority of female had trust on them to run their own business in future hence chi square value is 25.807= .000. This proves that majority believes that they will run their own business in future.

6. The Study found that majority believes that generally, society members accept an entrepreneurial career of women hence chi square value is 32.535=.000 this proves that majority believes that society members accept an entrepreneurial career.

7. The study found that majority of the respondents had opinion that social setup is a barrier for female own choice of profession.

Discussion

The current study aimed to make psychological analysis of career aspiration among women entrepreneurship choices at gradates level. The responses of the question of respondent of preferred choices include the following ranking 1. Teaching 2. Medical 3. Entrepreneurship. The researches on said topic were not conducted earlier because choices differ regionally academically and gender wise. A research was conducted in 2018 by (Chwarie Teg Summary report 2018) which explored choices of subject hence our research is more about career choice. The study of Chawarie 2018 also supported my study result that it is also important to note the influence of parents, which can be positive, but can also have a negative impact where gendered perceptions of particular careers and job roles held by parents can steer young women in a different direction. Some parents don't realize they are limiting their daughter's potential by assigning them a certain job because they are a girl. Numerous barrier that women Entrepreneur face when starting and growing their business these are culture constrain financial problem, through this research it has been observed that females are somehow still facing the barrier in their career progression. Financial barriers were seen as the biggest issue by the majority of young women. Concerns about increasing debt and cost of living are serious worries, which can push young women to move into any form of employment after university, due to the un affordability of further learning or work experience. The employment they go into may not utilize their full potential, and can lead young women away from their desired career path.

Conclusion

Women's career aspirations have continuously developed during the twentieth century, resulting in higher rates of female workforce involvement. Over the years, a variety of variables have influenced and hampered women's job aspirations and advancement. Women's job choices and the factors that influence them are important topics to investigate. Women's entrepreneurship appears to be a difficult issue in our society in AJ&K, where social and religious obligations may prevent her from becoming socially and religiously free. Entrepreneurship is currently the most discussed and encouraged concept all over the world

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to overcome economic challenges. Women, as the most important gender in the population, have enormous potential to contribute to a country's overall economic development. Women entrepreneurs confront numerous obstacles when starting and growing their businesses, including cultural constraints, a lack of business skills, financial difficulties, and a lack of business educational programs. Through this research it has been observed that females are somehow still facing the barrier in their career progressions.

In short, the findings of this study provide greater understanding in predicting student's entrepreneurial behavior. Besides that, it gives insights for the government and respective agencies to develop effective policies and programs to promote entrepreneurial mindset among the female of technical and vocational education. A well-established entrepreneurial environment is required to inspire and enable women to start their own firms." Encouragement of entrepreneurship from the ground up will lead to long-term remedies to societal inequalities. More boot mentorship and training facilities, as well as networking opportunities, are needed for women. Women have the potential to be a key driving force for economic progress and prosperity if given the correct encouragement and support. Financially and technically support need to be provided. More Entrepreneurship need to be explore and presented in job orientation days. Successful women stories need to be included at bachelor and master level. Government is unable to accommodate all jobs seeker hence it is important for government to offer different entrepreneurship opportunities. Government should starts providing assistance to the female entrepreneurs that include training, fund, specialist advice etc. Need to be the Removal of gender inequality. Encourage participation of women in income generating activities.

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